

MADRAS

D5.10 Project Website

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1.0	29/06/2020	Rosa Araujo	Project Coordinator

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Executive summary

This deliverable explains how MADRAS project webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. This document summarizes the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project. Also, the data protection measures adopted within the site.

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List of abbreviations

<i>CMS</i>	<i>Content Management System</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>IME</i>	<i>In Mould Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

MADRAS project aims to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

Four high performance materials to be developed in MADRAS tackle high cost, instability and short lifetime of OLAE devices under operational conditions through the development of robust alternatives and innovative approaches.

MADRAS project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of robust series of flexible plastronic products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection, will facilitate a faster up-taking.

Therefore, MADRAS proposes two products for persons' authentication market and smart manufacturing that will show a step forward towards digitisation and Internet of Things for its contribution to the sustainable deployment of smart products for consumer use. Ethical issues for these matters are properly addressed.

EUT is the partner responsible for **Task 5.7 Communication Activities**, aiming at providing all the communication materials useful for conveying the project to a broad group of users. The activity includes the creation and maintenance of the project's public website, which has been done by EUT with the support of all partners during M2 and M3. This document presents the website structure, content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

Public project website

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing the official MED4Youth project website. The registered URL is www.madras-project.eu.

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. **The website will be the anchor for all communication activities related to the project** and will serve as a **central point of entry for all public material, including the project's basic information**, expected impacts and project demonstrators. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active at least during two years after the project's finalization.

The website platform **follows the corporate visual identity of the project** created by Eurecat and approved by partners, and it gives access to MADRAS social media channels (Twitter so far).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use **WordPress**, as the Eurecat's Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website languages, the basis is English but if a need to translate some parts of the website arise, a multilingual plugin will be installed for this purpose.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

1. Website Structure

The following information architecture for MADRAS website is proposed:

Figure 1: MADRAS website structure. Pages in yellow colour will be developed during project execution as soon as communication and dissemination materials are created.

2. Website content

The texts hereinafter describe the contents published in the website.

2.1 Home

It includes one slider: **“ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS - Next generation of plastronic products: New materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable production of Organic Large Area Electronics (OLAE) devices”**.

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, main objectives, demonstrators, section on partners and link to newsletter subscription.

As soon as the “News and events” sections have some articles a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s twitter feed will be created.

In a nutshell

Developing low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products.

MADRAS is conceived to **enable the future market deployment of flexible and wearable OLAE-based products**, guaranteeing the use of industrially and environmentally sustainable materials and processes that are attractive to the market for their advanced functionalities, robustness, durability and safety.

During the project, a **set of new materials to be used as inks for the development of flexible OLAE products** will be produced with improved electrical and optical properties compared with current materials.

These materials, combined with the benefits brought by injection moulding, thermoforming and printed electronics, will build on an **industrially scalable manufacturing methodology** to improve OLAE-devices durability by encapsulation, reducing device manufacturing costs and increasing productivity rates.

BUTTON LINK - Find out more

Key outputs

4 columns with icons illustrating each of the concepts

- **Cost competitiveness** - Cost reduction of 30% due to an increased manufacturing yield when compared with non in-moulded devices
- **Durability** - Enhanced device lifetime thanks to the application of robust materials and encapsulation
- **Processability** - development of transparent conducting inks and paper-based substrates
- **Easier assembly process** - New manufacturing platform based on a modular approach that allows rapid industrial production of devices

Demonstrators

The innovative technology developed during the project will be demonstrated and implemented into two different demonstrators of plastic-embedded printed electronics

Geotracking flexible tag

New smart tag as a flexible self-adhesive label with a rigid electronic unit with enhanced geolocalisation features

Biometric photosensor

Fingerprint reader with a biometric sensor for the identification of users

Newsletter sign up

Stay in touch!

Subscribe now to be updated on MADRAS project development and latest news on Plastronics and Organic and Large Area Electronics

News & events

This section will include a Twitter widget and will show the latest news and events published.

Consortium

MADRAS interdisciplinary consortium is formed by 12 partners from 5 European countries. 6 SMEs, 1 large company, 3 research institutes, 1 university and 1 standardisation body

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS

Next generation of plastronic products

New materials and manufacturing processes for a scalable production of Organic Large Area Electronics (OLAE) devices

In a nutshell

Developing low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products

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[Find out more](#)

Key outputs

Cost competitiveness

Cost reduction of 30% due to an increased manufacturing yield when compared with non in-moulded devices

Processability

Development of transparent conducting inks and paper-based substrates

Durability

Enhanced device lifetime thanks to the application of robust materials and encapsulation

Easier assembly process

New manufacturing platform based on a modular approach that allows rapid industrial production of devices

Demonstrators

The innovative technology developed during the project will be demonstrated and implemented into **two different demonstrators of plastic-embedded printed electronics**.

Geotracking flexible tag

New smart tag as a flexible self-adhesive label with a rigid electronic unit.

More info

Biometric photosensor

Fingerprint reader with a biometric sensor for the identification of users.

More info

Stay in touch!

Subscribe now to be updated on MADRAS project development and latest news on Plastronics and Organic and Large Area Electronics

Subscribe

Our Team

MADRAS interdisciplinary consortium is formed by **12 partners** from **5 European countries**. **6 SMEs**, **1 large company**, **3 research institutes**, **1 university** and **1 standardisation body**.

In-mould electronics

Conductive and semi-conductive inks

Translucent and conductive papers

Research on Ink formulations

Innovative polymeric materials

Standardisation

Sensor technologies and flexible electronics

Industrial manufacturer

End user of the geotracking tag

Organic electronics

Legal, ethical and social impact

End user of the biometric photosensor

Figure 2: View of MADRAS homepage

2.2 About MADRAS

*This section includes the main information on the project, the main goals and the expected impact. When promotional materials (leaflet, rollup, etc.) and scientific publications are produced, specific sub-pages will be created to allocate them.
The content of the page is divided in the following sub-sections / areas:*

About MADRAS project

Novel advanced materials and production processes for a mass production of OLAE-based devices

The EU-funded MADRAS project aims to **boost the production of organic and large-area electronics (OLAE)** by establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology with new materials based on in-mould hybrid and printed electronics (IME).

The main innovation behind MADRAS relies on developing advanced materials to be promptly processed via IME to fabricate a **new generation of plastronic products with enhanced properties to make OLAE-based devices more affordable and durable.**

MADRAS materials and production process will be validated in **two different demonstrators** [LINK TO DEMONSTRATORS PAGE], including a biometric photosensor for **user identification** and a **geotracking flexible tag**.

The production methodology

A new device manufacturing process combining injection moulding and printed electronics

With the combination of two different manufacturing processes such as printed electronics and injection moulding and thermoforming [LINK IME page], MADRAS project will develop an **innovative and scalable manufacturing methodology** to improve OLAE-devices durability by encapsulation and reduce device manufacturing costs and high productivity rates.

The project idea to use In-Mould Electronics (IME) to manufacture OLAE-based devices originates from proof of concept tests at Eurecat laboratories which demonstrate that injection moulding can protect rigid-soft electronic interfaces with high thermal dissipation. Previous research was performed under the framework of [Optintegral](#) and [Optogenerapy](#) project applied to flexible displays.

Novel materials

Improved materials in terms of conductivity, charge mobility and transparency

A sustainable conductive substrate and advanced inks will be developed and implemented as Transparent Conductive Electrodes (TCE) and Hole Transport Layers (HTL), allowing the development of devices by printing techniques with increased robustness, while reducing their cost and environmental impact.

- Conductive and transparent paper substrates
- Transparent conductive silver nanowires-based inks
- Semiconducting transparent ink based on organic components
- Semiconductor inks based on metal oxide nanoparticles

Project timeline

1. Materials improvement
2. Design and printing of materials and control circuits
3. Demo products manufacturing
4. Validation and demonstration of materials
5. Processing and demonstrators in relevant environments

About MADRAS project

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The main innovation behind MADRAS relies on developing advanced materials to be promptly processed via IME to fabricate a **new generation of plasmonic products with enhanced properties to make OLAE-based devices more affordable and durable.**

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Do you want to know more about MADRAS?

Send us an email and we will get in touch with you as soon as possible.

Contact us!

Figure 3: View of about MADRAS page

2.2.1 OLAE

Organic and Large Area Electronics

Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE) is a new branch of electronics that works on **conductive polymers, plastics, or small molecules** OLAE devices are made of carbon-based materials which are widely available, cheaper and less toxic than traditional silicon-based electronics. This emerging technology is ideal for applications that require flexibility and adaptability to large areas, particularly paper and plastic.

Their conformability for large-area manufacturing opens up implementation in industrial application for energy harvesting, surface lighting, displays, wearables, biosensors, wearables, IoT, etc. Some examples are Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLED), the main building blocks of ultra-thin/rollable flat screens and handheld displays, and Organic Photovoltaics (OPV) which are used for clean-energy generation.

OLAE technologies and components have experienced a remarkable increase in usage in recent years thanks to printed electronics technologies progress, which offer solutions to develop OLAE thinner, more power-efficient, flexible and lightweight devices. However, the manufacturing processes for these devices are difficult to adapt to mass production due to significant open challenges, such as stability and processability.

Benefits

- Lightweight
- Flexible
- Thin
- Robust
- Stretchable

OLAE Market

According to leading IDTechEx, OLAE devices market will exponentially expand over the next ten years: growing from \$41.2 Billion in 2020 to \$74 billion in 2030. The OLAE industry is evolving at a very healthy pace and the demand of more flexible, compact and power efficient electronics' products is increasing.

OLAE has successfully entered in emerging fields such as IoT, automotive, healthcare, logistics, packaging and wearables. Numerous advantages of In-Mold Electronics (light weighting, space-saving, robustness, freedom of design) make it possible that the technology also can outstand in particular applications in the automotive industry, aerospace industry or appliances.

Adaptation of OLAE market snapshot with main data.
Source: IDTechEx 2019

OLAE – Organic and Large Area Electronics

Home / OLAE – Organic and Large...

Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE)

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2019 Market Snapshot

Source: IDTechEx 2019. Adaptation of OLAE market snapshot with main data.

Figure 4: View of OLAE page <https://madras-project.eu/olae/>

2.2.2 IME

In-Mould Electronics

IME combines the functional printing of electronics and the hybridisation of electronic components with traditional plastic transformation processes, such as thermoforming and injection.

IME will be employed in MADRAS project [LINK BACK TO PROJECT PAGE] as an integration process, targeting recyclability and good moisture barriers, and ad hoc connectors; and as a fabrication process of the advanced materials proposed in the project.

A revolution in the manufacture that allows to add intelligence and functions to the plastic components

The potential of IME is so huge that Eurecat has opened a [plastronics pilot plant](#), the first of these characteristics in Europe, to scale up research in new materials and processes in the IME field, which is a very convenient facility and starting point for MADRAS project.

Manufacturing process steps

Printing: Additive deposition of inks with electronic properties onto plastic substrates, with the aim of producing functional films containing thin layers of circuits and electronic devices.

Hybridisation: Placing electronic SMDs (surface-mount devices) components onto a functional film using pick and place equipment. The combination of printed electronics and SMD components is known as hybrid electronics.

Thermoforming: Controlled deformation using a mould of the printed sheets and hybridised rigid components to transform 2D films into 3D shapes.

Injection: 3D films coating with plastic materials by pressure-injecting melted plastic into a closed mould and allowing it to solidify inside.

IME advantages

- Reduction in the complexity of plastic products (fewer parts).
- Automation of assembly processes. Conventional “monolithic” manufacturing processes are replaced with a single part that does not require any assembly during production.
- Integration of electronics into products that have geometrically complex 3D shapes.
- Reduction in thickness (up to 80%) and weight (components are up to 60% lighter than traditional PCBs)
- Increased functionality.
- More durable electronics, as they are embedded/protected.
- Greater freedom to design products with new shapes and functionalities.

IME – In-Mould Electronics

Home / IME – In-Mould Electronics

In-Mould Electronics

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- Increased functionality.
- More durable electronics, as they are embedded/protected.

Figure 5: View of IME page: <https://madras-project.eu/in-mould-electronics/>

2.2.3 Partners

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. The page includes a first section with a short description of the consortium and a map of the location of MADRAS partners, followed by a portfolio with the logos of the different partners, leading to a specific page per partner with their contact details

MADRAS Project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising 12 partners from 5 European countries showing leadership in manufacturing flexible electronic devices, printed and in mould electronics, plastic processes, printed sensors and ink development.

6 SMEs, 1 large company, 3 research institutes, 1 university and 1 standardisation body

Eurecat

eurecat Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to MADRAS

With a vast experience in developing innovative solutions based on smart functional materials and devices, Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project and leading the IMHyPE process development. We are also responsible for carrying out environmental and costs effective analyses and managing IPR and the project's communication and dissemination activities.

www.eurecat.org

Twitter: @Eurecat_News

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/>

Youtube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ__t_6ozc7bDaKZw

Ethicas

Ethicas Research and Consulting is a Spain-based SME founded in 2012 as a university spin-off. Since then, Ethicas has been working on the legal, ethical and social impact of security policy, innovation and technology development, as well as the interaction between changing societal values, engineering possibilities and fundamental rights.

Ethicas Research and Consulting is specialized in the field of technologies and security, with particular focus on data protection and algorithmic fairness.

MADRAS

Eticas provides comprehensive solutions to problems within four areas of action: Research: we conduct research on the interactions between technology and society; Consulting: we help companies understand how to govern data ethically and responsibly; Cities: we support cities with the development and execution of responsible data strategies; Products: we are developing products that will help safeguard the privacy of your data.

Contribution to MADRAS

Eticas' area contribution to MADRAS is supporting partners on the social, ethical and data protection implications of the project research activities and outcomes. In this framework, it will also assess the acceptability and desirability of MADRAS technologies.

<https://www.eticasconsulting.com/>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/eticasconsult/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eticas-research-&-consulting/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9MVDikVsPMzyUPtzO8CVIA/videos>

GenesInk

GenesInk enables its customers to connect today the objects of tomorrow by reducing devices form factor and enabling new designs and products.

GenesInk is a French advanced material manufacturer of innovative highly conductive and semi-conductive inks founded in 2010 with currently 18 employees. Our products are made of metallic and semi-metallic nanoparticles synthesized on GenesInk manufacturing pilot lines and incorporated in unique coatings and nanoink formulations. Our nanoink solutions are adapted to the electronics markets and particularly the new printed electronic market: IoT, sensors, screens, lights, etc. using all industrial additive printing processes: Inkjet, Screen-printing, Flexography, Rotogravure, Spray, Slot-Die. Specifically designed for R2R printing methods, GenesInk products give high performances such as transparency and conductivity onto flexible substrates and offer a true alternative to commonly used deposition methods.

Contribution to MADRAS

Within MADRAS, GenesInk will be involved in the improvement of Ag nanowires based nanoinks for the bottom transparent electrode and of WO_x nanomaterials synthesis, doping and then formulation onto nanoinks for Hole Transport Layers (HTL). GenesInk will also participate in screen printing, inkjet printing and spray printing tests needed to assess the characterisation of the printed layers.

<https://www.genesink.com/>

Twitter @genesink

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/genesink/>

TECNOPACKAGING

TECNOPACKAGING is a leading technology-based SME involved in the development of innovative polymeric materials and their transformation processes for packaging and industrial plastic applications, targeting companies which operate directly or indirectly in the agri-food, cosmetic, pharmaceutical and industrial sectors.

Thanks to the capabilities and skills of their researchers and business developers, TECNOPACKAGING integrates the necessary technical equipment for providing customers a comprehensive design of new products, from concept to prototype, including validation and development of the first series.

Contribution to MADRAS

TECNOPACKAGING, as the leader impact boosting activities, will perform market up-taking and replication activities and will act as broker for the products developed within the project. Additionally, to diminish time to market and maximize exploitation success, TECNOPACKAGING will show MADRAS demos to its customer networks to open MADRAS solutions to new strategic markets. It will also participate in the quality and management procedures established in WP6.

<https://tecnopackaging.com/en/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/tecnopackaging>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/Tecnopackaging/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/tecnopackaging/>

Youtube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ_t_6ozc7bDaKZw

TNO

TNO is an independent applied research institution with a staff of ±3000 people and an annual turnover exceeding €400M€. TNO maintains close contacts with universities and basic research institutions in order to translate up-to-date knowledge and insights into practical applications. Clients include government, large companies and SME's. TNO will contribute to this project via its Business Unit Holst Centre. Holst Centre

is an independent open-innovation R&D center that develops generic technologies for Wireless Autonomous Sensor Technologies and Flexible Electronics. Holst Centre has over 200 employees from 28 nationalities.

Contribution to MADRAS

TNO will focus on processing technology for large thin film transistor backplanes. Using this technology, TNO will provide backplanes for the envisioned organic photodetector demo. TNO will also process the thin film encapsulation and will contribute to activities on system

MADRAS

integration and characterization on this demo. TNO will actively participate in thermoforming activities.

<https://www.holstcentre.com/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/holstcentre?lang=es>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/holst-centre/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWxYYkklvAbdBJJw6FIMX4g>

infinityPV

infinityPV is an SME which has specialized in roll-to-roll (R2R) printing/coating of organic electronics (OE) and in the development of OE research equipment.

infinityPV offer customized development work on printed technology including ink development, sensors, solar cells, specialized printing equipment, automation, etc. We manufacture flexible organic solar cells, electronics, R2R equipment, characterization equipment and OPV materials.

infinityPV is focused on supporting the development of R2R printed solar cell technology within academia and industry through open sharing of the technology and through education and through novel applications.

Contribution to MADRAS

Having extensive experience with printing and upscaling infinityPV is in charge of the validation process of the upscaled IMHyPE process and in defining a road map for scale up for mass markets. In addition to this infinityPV will lead the exploitation activities identifying exploitable results, barriers for exploitation and development of a business plan.

<https://infinitypv.com/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/infinitypv>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/infinitypv-aps>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/infinityPV>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/infinityPV>

COC

COC is research organization working in the field of organic materials for organic electronics and photoactive applications.

COC has R&D activities targeted on the industrial realization. Company is able to do optimization of new technologies and up-scale them from laboratory preparation up to pilot plant production. COC is involved in EU as well as national projects and offer the direct services to industrial entities.

MADRAS

Contribution to MADRAS

The synthesis and optimization of conductive polymers for applications in the final devices will be solved in the COC laboratories. The up scaling of inks formulation will be done at the same time.

<https://cocltd.cz/en>

No Social Media

University of Pardubice

University of Pardubice (UPA) is a modern and dynamic public higher education institution located in the Czech Republic. Its 7 faculties provide Bachelor's, Master's and Doctoral degree courses in 60 undergraduate or postgraduate study programmes to 8000 students.

Apart from teaching, the University is also renowned for its numerous scientific and research activities, in which it has been ranked among the top ten higher education institutions in the Czech Republic, mainly due to scientific results of the Faculty of Chemical Technology. Research and development (R&D) have been carried out on a broad scale, ranging from fundamental to specific applied research. Current research partners include industry, businesses and companies, R&D departments of other institutions and jointly operated laboratories, creating also consortia and clusters. The Centre for technology and knowledge transfer helps to link scientific capacities to practise and actively promote the intellectual property assets of the University.

Contribution to MADRAS

Within project the UPA team will be responsible for research and development of ink formulations of conductive polymers (PEDOT, PPY, PANI) for fabrication of HTL (Hole transport layer) or transparent conductive layers (TCL) using printing or coating technologies.

Alongside this, UPA team will be responsible for development of technology printing/coating processes for HTL and TCL layers fabrication with required electrical and morphological properties.

<https://fcht.upce.cz/en>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/UniPardubice>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-pardubice/>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/fchtupa/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/user/upcecz>

UNE

The Spanish Association for Standardization, UNE, is legally designated as the National Standardization Body of Spain. It is the national representative at the European (CEN and CENELEC), International (ISO and IEC) and Pan-American (COPANT) Standards

MADRAS

Organizations, and member of the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

Formally, it is a non-profitmaking, private, independent and multisectoral organisation, recognised at National, European and International levels. Through the development of technical standards helps improving the quality, competitiveness and innovation of companies, products and services.

Contribution to MADRAS

UNE has a large experience in supporting research and innovation communities when taking advantage of standards and standardization to increase the impact of their activities, approaching their results to the industry, society and market environments. With this aim, UNE will lead all standardization-related activities in MADRAS.

<https://www.une.org/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/NormasUNE>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/une-asociaci%C3%B3n-espa%C3%B1ola-de-normalizaci%C3%B3n/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCl1cbwOPrFUxcq4yf61jIzw>

Arjowiggins

arjowiggins

Arjowiggins is a private company, one of the world's leading producers of fine, smart and technical papers as well as security papers.

Some of its most prestigious well-known ranges are Conqueror, Curious Collection, Keaycolour, Pop'Set, Rives for corporate communication and luxury packaging, or Gateway for technical drawing, and more recently Powercoat and Alive, specially adapted for printed electronics and connected papers.

Arjowiggins is now the first and leading company in intelligent papers, ready to print in graphic printing to create smart paper products.

Arjowiggins has pilots located especially in its R&D center in Voiron (France) and industrial roll to roll flexo printing unit dedicated to printed electronics, mainly printing, up to now, NFC and UHF antenna. The number of employees is around 800 people for the group.

Contribution to MADRAS

In the frame of the MADRAS project, Arjowiggins will develop an improved version of the translucent and conductive paper, with 2 main goals: improving the transparency of the translucent base paper and decreasing the electrical resistance of the Ag Nw layer.

<https://powercoatpaper.com>

MADRAS

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/ArjoCreatives>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/arjowiggins-creative-papers/>

Cooltra Motosharing

Cooltra Group is the leading company in sustainable mobility solutions on two wheels in Europe. It is present in 6 countries in Europe (Spain, Austria, France, Italy, Portugal and the Czech Republic), and has a workforce of 1,000 employees. It currently has a fleet of 17,000 vehicles, of which 56% are electric scooters that operate by emitting a zero footprint.

Cooltra Group offers two-wheel mobility solutions ranging from scooters rental for days, -oriented to customers who need a scooter for their vacations-, to rental for months for individuals, companies and public administrations.

The company is the market leader in number of vehicles, it is present in more than 20 cities and offers up to 100 points where customers can pick up their vehicles.

The company has 3 brands: Cooltra, mobility solutions for both individuals and companies or institutions, eCooltra, launched in 2016 and based on the rental of electric motorcycles by minutes, and EcoScooting, last mile delivery service within cities through vehicles 100% electric.

Contribution to MADRAS

Cooltra will provide the end platform to test in a real vehicle the biometric photosensor to validate user's identity. We are responsible of assembling the prototype and performing the needed endurance tests and UX validation.

www.corporate.cooltra.com/en/

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/cooltra>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cooltra-motos-s-l-/?viewAsMember=true>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/CooltraMotos>

Youtube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCR9EGPcQt01-_BbAx315SsA

Unwinloc

MADRAS

UWINLOC is a French SME founded by two entrepreneurs in 2015. Currently they hire 30 employees with multidisciplinary background Engineering, Business Development, Legal/IP with a clear focus in integrated IoT technology for smart and efficient asset management.

Its current solution is an important leap forward compared to existing technologies. In fact, to address several markets, the solution will allow companies to locate, identify, and track thousands of objects indoors continuously, reliably, accurately, and at a low cost. To address these requirements, UWINLOC solution offers several major technological breakthroughs, protected by patents (to date: 12 patents application).

Contribution to MADRAS

UWINLOC is the end user of the Smart Geotracking tag. They will propose a tangible demonstrator to exhibit the maturity and a concrete use-case for the technology developed during the project. By integrating the flexible smart tag developed during the MADRAS project to its existing system, UWINLOC will be able to put forward the existing need for development of OLAE and flexible electronics in the industry 4.0 sector and more precisely in the indoor location market.

<https://uwinloc.com>

Twitter <https://twitter.com/uwinloc>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/UWINLOC/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/uwinloc/>

Consortium

MADRAS Project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising **12 partners** from **5 European countries** showing leadership in manufacturing flexible electronic devices, printed and in mould electronics, plastic processes, printed sensors and ink development.

6

SMEs

1

Large company

3

Research institutes

1

University

1

Standardisation body

Eurecat
Read more »

Eticas Research and Consulting
Read more »

Genesink
Read more »

TECNOPACKAGING
Read more »

Figure 6: View of Partners' page: <https://madras-project.eu/about-us/partners/>

2.3 MADRAS demonstrators

New plastronic products

MADRAS project will demonstrate and validate the novel production methodology and materials [LINK TO ABOUT THE PROJECT PAGE] in two products: a **biometric photosensor for fingerprint users' recognition** of a scooter-sharing company and a **geotracking flexible tag** for the packaging and logistics sector.

The products reflect not only large market potential applications of flexible and wearable electronics, but also demonstrate the unique MADRAS technology approach based on applying advanced materials and soft fabrication techniques in the development of OLAE devices [LINK OLAE PAGE].

MADRAS's relevance lays in the capacity of creating new plastronic products but also new categories of products, as well as to include new technology into traditional products with seamless integration.

- **Hybrid printed circuit development:** A proof-of-concept demonstration developed based on a manufacturing open platform technology that allows various devices to be fabricated in a modular approach.
- **Printed device development:** Development of printed devices with enhanced functionalities and user-centred design making use of advanced materials and processes.
- **Digitisation:** Sensors and circuits controlled by hardware/software and communication systems ensuring data privacy and security.
- **Fast assembly of components:** The deposition of the materials and the subsequent in mould encapsulation will allow rapid industrial production of robust devices to address cost competitiveness in the evolving plasmonic market.

Geotracking flexible tag

Flexible tag to be attached to objects such as tools, vehicles and parts in assembly lines compatible with curved surfaces for their geolocalisation in UWINLOC facilities.

An important innovation of the demo will be the implementation of an RF energy harvesting system through its antenna that will enable a battery free tag.

Traditional electronics (PCB and protective casing) limit the type of objects to track based on shape and surface material.

In MADRAS project, the new smart tag will be prepared as a flexible self-adhesive label with a rigid electronic unit with optimised power energy management and enhanced geolocalisation features.

Biometric reader

Fingerprint biometric reader based on photodetection for the users' identification.

The readers will be integrated into eCooltra shared scooters, aiming to increase the user security and decrease vandalism. For the improvement of the users' authentication, the fingerprint reader will include an additional heart rate sensing functionality by using NIR

photoactive materials.

Current biometric photosensors are mainly based on silicon-based rigid substrates and evaporated materials. MADRAS approach is based on the use of solution-based organic photoactive semiconductors and advanced inks in manufacturing processes that will give improved robustness and ease of integration.

Production process

✉ info@madras-project.com

MADRAS

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[ABOUT US](#)
[MADRAS DEMONSTRATORS](#)
[NEWS & EVENTS](#)
[CONTACT](#)

MADRAS demonstrators

Home / MADRAS demonstrators

New plastronic products

MADRAS project will demonstrate and validate the novel production methodology and materials in two products: a **biometric photosensor for fingerprint users recognition** of a scooter-sharing company and a **geotracking flexible tag** for the packaging and logistics sector.

The products reflect not only large market potential applications of flexible and wearable electronics, but also demonstrate the unique **MADRAS technology approach** based on applying advanced materials and soft fabrication techniques in the development of **OLAE devices**.

MADRAS's relevance lays in the capacity of creating new **plastronic products** but also new **categories of products**, as well as to include new technology into traditional products with seamless integration.

Hybrid printed circuit development

A proof-of-concept demonstration developed based on a manufacturing open platform technology that allows various devices to be fabricated in a modular approach.

Printed device development

Development of printed devices with enhanced functionalities and user-centred design making use of advanced materials and processes.

Digitisation

Sensors and circuits controlled by hardware/software and communication systems ensuring data privacy and security.

Fast assembly of components

The deposition of the materials and the subsequent in mould encapsulation will allow rapid industrial production of robust devices to address cost competitiveness in the evolving plastronic market.

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Current biometric photosensors are mainly based on silicon-based rigid substrates and evaporated materials. MADRAS approach is based on the use of solution-based organic photoactive semiconductors and advanced inks in manufacturing processes that will give improved robustness and ease of integration.

Figure 7: View of demonstrators page

2.4 News

This section is for publishing any news related to the project. i.e: about meetings, first results, publications, etc. News articles will be published regularly by Communication and Dissemination Leader Eurecat with inputs of all partners in order to generate content to feed the project's social media and increase the traffic to the website. News articles will be categorised in self-explanatory categories to facilitate filtering.

On the other hand, partner will contribute to this section with **regular blog posts** on project topics, starting at **M6 (September 2020)**, following guidelines prepared by EUT (see Annex 4). Partner's blog articles will be disseminated widely across MADRAS' channels and the based for regular newsletters. Partners are expected to contribute to the website with 2 blog posts during project execution.

2.4.1 Media

Section including the project's press releases and key media coverage on the project.

2.5 Events

This page will include an agenda announcing events where MED4Youth is attending / participating (conferences, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

2.6 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@madras-project.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

The screenshot shows the MADRAS website's contact page. At the top left is the MADRAS logo. A navigation menu includes links for HOME, ABOUT US, MADRAS DEMONSTRATORS, NEWS & EVENTS, and CONTACT (which is highlighted). Below the navigation is a teal header bar with the word 'Contact' on the left and 'Home / Contact' on the right. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a 'Contact us!' form with fields for 'Your Name (required)', 'Your Email (required)', 'Subject', and 'Your Message'. Below the message field is a checkbox for 'I have read and I accept the [privacy policy](#)' and a 'Send' button. The right column features a 'Coordinated by:' section with the name 'Rosa Araujo', the organization 'Eurecat Technology Center', and the location 'Barcelona, Spain'. Below this is an 'Email' section with the address 'info@madras-project.eu' and a 'Follow @MADRAS_EU' button.

Figure 8: View of MADRAS contact page

3. Layout

The website **menu is available from all pages**, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the site.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- MADRAS logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Acces to Social Media platforms (Twitter, YouTube - when created).

Footer

- EU logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862492. This website reflects only the author’s view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”*
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Link to newsletter subscription
- Contact info

4. Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The website will be updated from now on by the **Communication Leader Eurecat together with the inputs sent by all partners** every time a new dissemination action in done, a result is achieved, or there is other news worth publishing.

5. Analytics

The MADRAS website has installed **Matomo** in the platform’s back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site’s performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services or third parties.

Google Search Console will be used to upload the file robots.txt to make easier for Google Robots the indexation.

Figure 9: Matomo panel

6. Site hosting, installation & maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end and until two years after and adding content to the website. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that MADRAS website is well positioned in the browsers.

7. Data protection

MADRAS website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy on Annex.

8. Website KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of MADRAS Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the website performance. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>4.000
	Number Pages Viewed		>10.000
	Number page / session		>1.5
	Number users		>2.000
	Avg. session time		>3.00 min (70% of the users)

ANNEX

1. Legal warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website <https://www.madras-project.eu> is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

Access to the Website

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

Use of the Website

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

Operation of the website

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

Liability

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

Policy on links

a) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

b) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

Intellectual and industrial property rights of the content

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer

MADRAS

programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names ("distinctive signs") are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

Applicable legislation

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

Contact

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

2. Cookies Policy

Informational banner

This website uses its own and third-party cookies to collect statistical information on the browsing of users and improve their services with the preferences, generated from their browsing habits. We also inform you that this website complies with the provisions of the LSSI-CE and the GDPR. In this sense, cookies will not be stored in your terminal for the purposes that the User has not consented to.

What are cookies and why do we use them on the website?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

What type of cookies does the website use?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information

collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.

- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

More details about the cookies we use:

Necessary cookies

- **Name:** gdpr[allowed_cookies]
- **Provider:** madras-project.eu
- **Purpose:** stores cookies consent types
- **Expiry period:** 1 year

- **Name:** gdpr[consent_cookies]
- **Provider:** madras-project.eu
- **Purpose:** stores user cookies acceptance
- **Expiry period:** 1 year

Statistics cookies

- **Name:** _pk_ses.9.8960
- **Provider:** madras-project.eu
- **Purpose:** session cookies responsible for keeping the session active for 30 minutes.
- **Expiry period:** 1 day
- **Name:** _pk_id.9.8960
- **Provider:** madras-project.eu
- **Purpose:** user unique ID that is used to generate statistical data on how the visitor uses the website.
- **Expiry period:** 1 year and 1 month

Social Media cookies

- **Name:** _ga, _twitter_sess, _gid Eu_cn, Guest_id, Personalization_id, Tfw_exp.
- **Provider:** Twitter
- **Purpose:** Widget showing recent tweets published

Cookies on social networks

Some pages of our websites allow users to share our content through social networks, such as Facebook, Twitter, Googles, etc. Sometimes we post videos in sites like YouTube. These sites may set a cookie when you connect to their service, which we do not control. You may want to check their websites to learn more about their Cookies Policy.

Learn more about social media cookies:

<https://es-es.facebook.com/about/privacy/cookies>

<http://www.google.es/intl/es/policies/technologies/cookies/>

<https://twitter.com/privacy>

<http://es.about.pinterest.com/privacy/>

<https://help.instagram.com/155833707900388>

<https://vine.co/privacy>

<https://es.foursquare.com/legal/privacy>

<https://www.youtube.com/yt/policyandsafety/es/>

How can the user disable the browser cookies?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- [Information about cookies for Internet Explorer.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Mozilla Firefox.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Opera.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Google Chrome.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Safari.](#)

Additional information

For more information on the use of cookies and how to block them, go to www.allaboutcookies.org, www.youronlinechoices.eu. If you have any questions or comments about our use of cookies, please contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

3. Privacy Policy

Who is the data controller for your personal data?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

For what purpose will be processed your personal data?

Data received through the contact form will be used to manage your query or request.

On our website, there may be forms that collect your data for specific purposes. In these cases, you will be subject to the specific terms applicable to each case.

Is it mandatory to provide all the information requested in the forms on the website?

The user must complete the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

How long will your personal data be retained for?

Personal data will be retained for the duration of the purpose for which it was collected and while its erasure is not requested and consent is not revoked.

What is the lawful basis for us to process your personal data?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

What recipients will your data be shared with?

Personal data received through the forms of the website will be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the latest news about the project through periodic newsletters.

Your data will not be passed on to third parties, unless there is a legal obligation to do so. Should this case arise, authorisation will be sought first from the concerned parties.

What are your rights regarding your personal data?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data to be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org.

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

What security measures has the institution implemented?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

Social media

MADRAS, a project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which MADRAS an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

4. Blog posts guidelines

We envision 2 types of articles to be posted on the website according to its length: short and large ones.

- **Short articles:** are up to 500 words and can be written for the general public or for the scientific and academic community. Normally this kind of articles would include one or more hyperlinks to other content (either written by us or by other party not related to MADRAS Project).
- **Large articles:** standalone articles that are from 700 to 1000 words long. Aimed to the scientific and academic community but can be also read by interested persons from the general public (please try to limit acronyms and specialized jargon or explain it somewhere within the article itself). It might contain links as well but mostly to support material or cited sources.

Both types of articles should be supported with at least one picture, diagram, graphic or maybe more.

- More scientific kind of articles will be well dressed with graphics and diagrams which support the text. These diagrams or graphics should be provided by the author since they are closely related to the content and would be difficult to produce otherwise.
- General images would be provided by Eurecat as MADRAS Communication and Dissemination Leader. If you need specific ones, you can either provide them yourself or work with us to identify a good image.
- We will set up a small bank of images in Sharepoint to be used for this purpose.

The **topics recommended** for these articles are:

- Organic and large area electronics (OLAE)
- In-mold printed electronics
- Manufacturing processes and methodologies
- Materials, inks, layers development
- MADRAS demonstrators
- All-printed organic photodetectors
- Biometric sensors
- Printed antenna
- Radio Frequency Energy harvesting
- Ultra-Wide Band antennas
- Flexible tag for geolocalization

4.1 Blog posts calendar

PARTNER	Blog post 1	Blog post 2
EUT	Sep-20	Jan-22
GNK	Oct-20	Feb-22
AWCP	Nov-20	Mar-22
UPA	Jan-21	Apr-22
COC	Feb-21	May-22
ETR	Mar-21	Jun-22
UWL	Apr-21	Sep-22
TNG	May-21	Oct-22
UNE	Jun-21	Nov-22
TNO	Sep-21	Jan-23
ERC	Oct-21	Feb-23
INF	Nov-21	Mar-23